

1 **Postharvest ripeness assessment of ‘Hass’ avocado**
2 **based on development of a new ripening index**
3 **and Vis-NIR spectroscopy**

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13 **Abstract**

14 Postharvest ripening in avocados (*Persea americana* Mill.) is a complex process in which many
15 different quality parameters including texture and flesh firmness (FF) undergo changes.
16 Nowadays, warehouses classify fruit ripeness by testing a small number of individual avocados,
17 using destructive techniques to determine flesh firmness and dry matter content (DMC), even
18 though DMC shows little change during postharvest ripening. This destructive testing procedure
19 generates waste and does not fully quantify inhomogeneity within different batches that go
20 through the ripening process.

21 This paper has two aims: i. to evaluate a non-destructive method to classify avocados in three
22 classes predefined by a warehouse, based on destructive FF tests performed on a small number

23 of avocados. The proposed method is based on Vis-NIR spectroscopy (380-2000 nm) together
24 with Partial Least Square Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA). This classification showed a satisfactory
25 general accuracy of 62 %, with 100 % well-classified samples in Classes 1, 20 % in Class 2 and 65
26 % in Class 3. ii. to improve classification a ripening index (RI) was developed, which combines
27 FF and DMC. The discrimination ability in the three classes was tested using Wilk's lambda,
28 calculated as between-class variance to the total variance ratio. Results showed values of 0.648
29 for RI, 0.516 for FF and 0.038 for DMC. A regression model was subsequently developed using
30 Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression to predict RI using Vis-NIR spectroscopy in an independent
31 dataset. The PLS results were satisfactory with the whole spectrum wavelength range (380-2000
32 nm), with R^2 of 0.62, SEP of 0.69, but presented a large bias value of 1.22. The same occurs in
33 models developed in the wavelength range from 400 to 1100 nm, with R^2 of 0.63, SEP of 0.68
34 and bias of 1.03. This could be corrected using a bias and slope correction algorithm. Study of
35 the correlation coefficients of the PLS regression models showed that the region 400-1100 nm
36 has a huge influence in the model, which indicates the potential of using cost-effective short Vis-
37 NIR spectrophotometers for RI prediction.

38 **Keywords:** *Dry matter content, flesh firmness, classification, chemometrics, PLS regression, non-*
39 *destructive.*

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47 1. INTRODUCTION

48 Avocado (*Persea americana* Mill.) is a climacteric fruit that experiences physiological changes
49 after harvest (Maftoonazad and Ramaswamy, 2005; Pinto et al., 2019). Avocados are normally
50 cultivated outside Europe, so before reaching the European continent they normally need to
51 travel long distances. To avoid the fruit damage, they are harvested when they have reached
52 the so-called physiological maturity, although they are still hard and green (Woolf et al., 2004).

53 After arriving at warehouses in Europe, avocados are ripened in chambers with ethylene
54 application and controlled temperature until they reach edible ripeness (Pedreschi et al., 2014).

55 Warehouses can manage the chambers' conditions to speed up or delay the ripening process
56 according to retailer demand. But avocado has a complex ripening physiology which makes
57 postharvest management difficult. In addition to their inability to ripen on the tree, their lengthy
58 flowering period, and environmental growing conditions, along with cultural practices, appear
59 to influence postharvest avocado ripening (Bower and Cutting, 1988; Hernández et al., 2016).

60 To manage postharvest fruit heterogeneity, the traditional standard for classifying 'Hass'
61 avocados was based on dry matter content (DMC) (UNECE 2017) as an indirect measurement of
62 water content. However, some warehouses do not base their postharvest classification on DMC
63 content due to its low variation during the ripening process. Some studies, such as the one
64 conducted by Pedreschi et al., (2014), found no correlation between the water content of
65 individual fruit and the time to reach edible ripeness, which indicates that DMC has an influence
66 at harvest time, though edible ripeness is affected by more factors (Hernández et al., 2016).

67 DMC can nevertheless be considered a quality parameter, since it highly correlates with oil
68 content (Hofman et al., 2013), which determines the smoothness of the fruit and hence
69 consumer acceptance. There are also other determinant variables for assessing the degree of
70 ripeness, i.e. texture, an important factor for consumer acceptance. Changes in texture are
71 found during the ripening process (Li et al., 2010), also associated to oil content (Chen et al.,

72 2009) and flesh firmness (FF) (Kassim et al., 2013). Therefore, to ensure correct classification, it
73 seems that not just one parameter should be considered, but rather a combination of different
74 factors. Indeed, a ripening level index which combines the lowest possible number of
75 parameters has been successfully applied in other fruit, such as mango (Rungpichayapichet et
76 al., 2016), and may be of interest in the classification of avocados.

77 Moreover, when suppliers need to measure DMC content and FF, they do so by means of
78 destructive techniques, which are expensive and time-consuming and produce food waste
79 (Magwaza and Tesfay, 2015). They also cannot inspect the whole batch and must consequently
80 sample a few fruit and classify all of them according to the small number actually examined. The
81 impossibility of testing more fruit causes inhomogeneity in the maturation chambers.

82 To overcome the issues associated with destructive testing, several non-destructive techniques
83 have been studied for fruit classification. These allow inspection of 100 % (or at least most) of
84 the production and are non-invasive and fast. Some have focused on determining FF by means
85 of image analysis, using a smartphone camera along with machine-learning techniques (Cho et
86 al., 2020). Landahl and Terry (2020) studied laser Doppler vibrometry to assess avocado fruit
87 firmness in the packhouse. To determine DMC, visible and near-infrared spectroscopy (Vis-NIR)
88 was widely used in several studies concerning avocado, such as those conducted by Olarewaju
89 et al. (2016), Blakey (2016), Ncama et al. (2018) and Subedi and Walsh (2020). However, even
90 though some of these techniques have already been implemented in the avocado industry, a
91 ripeness indicator which allows warehouses to separate avocados according to their ripening
92 stage is still lacking.

93 Taking all these factors into account, this study was conducted with two aims: to demonstrate
94 that Vis-NIR spectroscopy can distinguish avocado ripening classes defined by the warehouse
95 (classification using FF destructive analysis); and to develop a proof of concept of a ripening
96 index which can be used as a reference parameter to establish ripening stages for avocados.

97 Finally, this work also provides a partial least square regression (PLSR) model to predict the
98 ripening index with Vis-NIR spectroscopy, which could improve cool-chamber management in
99 warehouses.

100 **2. MATERIAL AND METHODS**

101 *2.1. Fruit sampling*

102 A total of N = 120 avocados (*Persea americana* Mill. cv Hass) were obtained directly from a fruit
103 warehouse in Bizkaia, Spain. Batches of 60 fruit were purchased in February and April 2018. Both
104 batches came from the same supplier, but from different origins. Samples from February 2018
105 were from Chile (mid-season) and samples from April 2018 came from South Africa (the
106 beginning of the season).

107 When the avocados are received in the warehouse facilities, a random sampling of 3-4 avocados
108 per pallet is done, to ensure they have a minimum of 22 % of DMC and an FF higher than 196-
109 215 N. These avocados will henceforth be designated as Class 1 (avocados at reception level).
110 Then, the fruit are stored in ripening chambers at 21 °C with ethylene until they reach an FF
111 around 117 – 137 N. These avocados will henceforth be designated as Class 2. Then, the
112 temperature of the chamber is lowed until around 8-10 °C and the fruit remain there until they
113 have reached the edible ripeness accepted by the retailer (7 – 39 N). These avocados are ready
114 for distribution and will be designated as Class 3. This process is continuous, as avocados are
115 constantly arriving, being ripened, and delivered to the retailer, which means that the three
116 classes are present in the warehouse at the same time. To decide when to change from one
117 Class to another, the warehouse test the FF of 3-4 avocados per pallet, selected randomly.

118 A total of 120 fruit were selected, imitating the warehouse sampling. 40 fruit were selected from
119 the different classes, distributed as follows:

- 120 - Class 1: Hard avocado, at reception level – $N_1 = 40$ avocados (20 fruit on February + 20
121 fruit on April).
- 122 - Class 2: Medium avocado, during the ripening process in the chambers – $N_2 = 40$
123 avocados (20 February + 20 April).
- 124 - Class 3: Ripe avocado, the ripening process has finished, and it is ready to be delivered
125 to the retailer – $N_3 = 40$ avocados (20 February + 20 April).

126 Vis-NIR spectra acquisition was carried out in two scanning sessions: one in February 2018 and
127 the other in April 2018. For each, the process was the following: the fruit was collected in the
128 warehouse (20 samples per class) and stored in a cool chamber at 4°C at AZTI facilities. After 24
129 hours the fruit were taken to Tekniker's laboratories, where the sampling was done. To ensure
130 correct sampling, avocados were chosen randomly from the three classes and submitted to the
131 tests. They were first scanned with the Vis-NIR equipment; flesh firmness was then measured
132 and finally the DMC.

133 *2.2. Vis-NIR spectrophotometer*

134 The spectra of 120 fruit were measured by a Perkin Elmer Lambda 950 spectrophotometer
135 (Figure 1A) with a 150 mm diameter PbS integrating sphere. The equipment included a
136 photomultiplier tube (PMT) R6872 detector for the UV/Vis region and a Peltier cooled lead-
137 sulphide (PbS) detector for the NIR region. Detector change is automatic during monochromator
138 slewing. Although the spectrometer acquires spectra ranging from 210 to 2500 nm, the
139 adjustments carried out during spectroscopic method definition indicate that the useful range
140 was between 380 and 2000 nm, with 5 nm data interval and 324 spectral bands. Thus, the other
141 wavelength ranges (210-379 nm) and above 2000 nm were discarded.

142 Instrumentation calibration was done using a white Spectralon® with 99 % reflectance
143 (Labsphere) as the reference material. Spectra were acquired in reflectance mode and
144 transformed to $-\log(R)$ for data analysis.

145 The measurements were made at room temperature (21 °C). Avocados were maintained at
146 room temperature before the scanning. Two spectra were acquired at the equator of the fruit
147 (Figure 1). Each measurement was made 180° from the other. For data analysis, the mean
148 spectrum of the two measurements was subsequently obtained, providing a 120-spectra
149 database.

150 *2.3. Destructive analysis*

151 *2.3.1 Flesh firmness*

152 The FF was measured with a penetrometer (PCE-FM200, PCE Instruments Southampton, UK)
153 equipped with a cylindrical probe with 8 mm diameter and was expressed in Newtons (N). To
154 ensure measurement reproducibility it was implemented on a test stand.

155 The FF was measured after the removal of small patches of skin at two locations along the fruit's
156 equator, coincident with the area where the spectra were taken (Figure 1). Each measurement
157 was made 180° from the other, and then the mean of the two measurements was obtained.

158 *2.3.2 Dry matter*

159 Destructive measurements of DMC were carried out for each avocado. Each fruit was cut into
160 slices 2 mm thick at the equatorial area, coincident with the region where the spectra were
161 taken (Figure 1). The slices were weighed and then heated in an oven at 80 °C until they reached
162 a constant weight. After that, they were weighed again. The DMC was computed as follows
163 (Equation 1):

$$164 \quad DMC (\%) = \frac{Dry\ weight}{Wet\ weight} \times 100$$

165 *Equation 1.*

166

167

Figure 1. Scheme of the sample where the measurements were taken from

168

169 *Table 1. Maximum (Max), minimum (Min), mean and standard deviation (SD) of dry matter content (DMC) and flesh*

170 *firmness (FF) and number of avocados (N) for each ripening class for data collected in February 2018 and April 2018*

		DMC (%)				FF (N)			
February 2018	N	Max	Min	Mean	SD	Max	Min	Mean	SD
Class 1	20	30.36	21.02	25.27	2.33	215.75	47.07	159.82	52.44
Class 2	20	30.23	21.14	25.04	2.43	66.34	11.96	35.18	16.93
Class 3	20	31.60	20.77	24.13	2.63	31.67	7.40	20.33	7.01
April 2018									
Class 1	20	20.92	15.45	18.18	1.64	123.37	28.73	54.72	23.78
Class 2	20	29.84	16.32	19.31	2.86	72.52	5.24	21.84	17.60
Class 3	20	25.27	20.17	22.60	1.47	16.57	2.55	7.42	3.75

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172 *2.4. Ripening Index development*

173 A ripening Index (RI) parameter was obtained considering both DMC and FF. The FF was linked

174 to factors such as colour change in cultivars such as 'Hass' (Cox et al., 2004); it is an accepted

175 parameter for assessing avocado ripeness (Köhne et al., 1998; White et al., 1999). DMC is

176 correlated to oil content, which contributes to the creaminess of avocados (Hofman et al., 2000).

177 Considering that FF decreases, and DMC increases with fruit maturation and both factors are
178 associated with ripening a RI was developed, inspired by previous work by Mahayothee et al.
179 (2007), as a function of FF and DMC (Eq. 2).

$$\text{Ripening Index (RI)} = \ln\left(\frac{FF}{DMC}\right)$$

180
181 *Equation 2.*

182 After determination of the RI, the class boundaries were redefined according to the results
183 obtained with the index, to minimise the overlap between the categories. Then, a confusion
184 matrix between the actual classes and the redefined classes was computed.

185 *2.5. Multivariate data analysis*

186 All calculations were carried out in Matlab R2017b and Matlab R2015b (The Mathworks, Natick,
187 USA). Multivariate data analysis was conducted using the PLS Toolbox (Eigenvector Research)
188 and other programs developed by the authors themselves, based in Matlab.

189 *2.5.1. Ripening parameter selection*

190 A Wilk's lambda test statistic was computed to choose which variable (among DMC, FF and RI)
191 was optimal to distinguish the three classes established by FF testing (Warehouse methodology).
192 In this case, the Wilk's lambda criterion chosen was the between-class variance to total variance
193 ratio (Lebart et al., 1984). This ratio ranges between 0 and 1; the higher the ratio, the better the
194 discrimination between classes.

195 *2.5.2. Spectral data pre-processing*

196 Prior to model building, data were pre-processed to remove irrelevant information such as
197 noise, scattering and additive and multiplicative effects induced by physical effects (Nicolai et
198 al., 2007). Several methods were tested: mean centring according to columns, standard normal
199 variate (SNV), standard normal variate detrend (SNVd), Savitzky-Golay's first and second
200 derivatives, and combinations of all these methods.

201 to optimise pre-processing with a derivative, changes in the parameters as a function of window
202 width (5-121) in the Savitzky-Golay algorithm were evaluated using the Wilk's lambda test
203 statistic.

204 *2.5.3. Dataset for model building*

205 The whole dataset ($N = 120$) was divided into a calibration ($N_{cal} = 60$) and a validation ($N_{val} = 60$)
206 subset. For that purpose, data from February 2018 were used as the calibration set and data
207 from April 2018 as an independent validation set. Both datasets, calibration and validation, had
208 the same number of avocados for each class (20 avocados for each class).

209 *2.5.4. Flesh Firmness classification model development*

210 After data pre-processing, a classification model was developed using partial least squares
211 discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) (Barker and Rayens, 2003). This is a linear method based on the
212 PLS2 algorithm, where the variable y is a dummy 3-column matrix that records the membership
213 of each observation. For each observation, a 1 is put in the column corresponding to the class it
214 belongs to (class defined by the warehouse, based on the FF) and 0 elsewhere. The PLS2 model
215 is calibrated on n Latent variables (nLV), producing nLV scores for each observation. The nLV
216 scores were inputted into a linear discriminant analysis (LDA), which produced two final scores
217 (3-1 degrees of freedom). The class attribution was done based on Mahalanobis distance.

218 The model was fitted using the calibration dataset $[X_{60 \times 325}, Y_{60 \times 1}]_{cal}$ to select the optimal value
219 of nLV by means of cross-validation (CV), which optimizes the model by dividing the dataset into
220 cross-validation groups. Each group is removed from the calibration set (one at a time) and the
221 model is trained without that group. The model is then validated using the removed group of
222 samples. After that, the next group is removed, and so on. In this study, CV was performed in 2
223 blocks, repeated 5 times.

224 Once the model was fitted, it was validated using the validation dataset $[X_{60 \times 325}, y_{60 \times 1}]_{\text{val}}$. The
225 performance of the models was evaluated using several performance metrics: (i) accuracy,
226 which is the ratio between the samples correctly classified to the total number of samples; (ii)
227 precision, which estimates the predictive value of the algorithm (Sokolova et al., 2006); (iii)
228 sensitivity, the proportion of positive samples that were correctly classified; and (iv) specificity,
229 the proportion of negative samples that were correctly classified. Finally, the F-1 score was
230 calculated. It is the harmonic mean of precision and sensitivity, and ranges from 0 to 1. The
231 higher the values of the F-1 score, the higher the classification performance (Tharwat, 2018).

232 *2.5.5 Prediction model development for RI prediction*

233 The prediction model was performed using PLSR, which is a linear multivariate method able to
234 relate two data matrices: the spectral data (X) and the quantitative value of the ripening index
235 (y), maximizing the covariance between X and y and creating components (LV) related to X and
236 y (Wold et al., 2001). The model was fitted using the calibration dataset $[X_{60 \times 325}, y_{60 \times 1}]_{\text{cal}}$ with
237 20 LV. As a cross-validation method, venetian blinds, with 1 in 5 samples out, was applied. To
238 select the optimum number of LVs, to give the minimum squared error and the maximum
239 coefficient of determination (R^2) between the lab-measured and the predicted values were
240 considered.

241 The performance of the models was assessed by applying them to the validation dataset $[X_{60 \times 325},$
242 $y_{60 \times 1}]_{\text{val}}$ and by the following criteria: bias, standard error of prediction (SEP), coefficient of
243 determination (R^2_{val}) and residual predictive deviation (RPD) (Equations 3, 4, 5 and 6).

$$244 \quad \text{Bias} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i - \hat{y}_i$$

245 *Equation 3.*

246
$$SEP = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i - Bias)^2}$$

247 *Equation 4.*

248
$$R^2 = \frac{[\sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}}) (y_i - \bar{y})]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

249 *Equation 5.*

250
$$RPD = \frac{std(y)}{SEP}$$

251 *Equation 6.*

252 being N the number of observations and y_i and \hat{y}_i the measured and the predicted value of the
 253 i^{th} observation, respectively; \bar{y} the average value of y_i and $\bar{\hat{y}}$ the average value of \hat{y}_i ; $std(y)$ the
 254 standard deviation of y .

255 **3. RESULTS**

256 *3.1. Definition of the best ripening parameter and RI boundary definition*

257 Results of the Wilk's lambda (w) analysis between the three ripening classes and the three
 258 studied parameters (DMC, FF and RI) shows that the predefined classes were only slightly related
 259 to DMC with a w_{DMC} value of 0.038. The boxplot shows that the 3 classes appear overlapped and
 260 thus they cannot be discriminated (Figure 2A). FF presents a higher value of $w_{\text{FF}} = 0.516$. In this
 261 case, the classes are slightly better discriminated, though a large spread is seen for Class 1
 262 (Figure 2B). Finally, w_{RI} shows a value of 0.648. The boxplot for RI shows better separation of the
 263 three classes and allows definition of boundaries (Figure 2C).

A

B

C

264 *Figure 2. Boxplots of the three studied parameters related to the three ripening classes ($N_{\text{Class 1}} = 40$; $N_{\text{Class 2}} = 40$;*
 265 *$N_{\text{Class 3}} = 40$). A. Dry matter content (%); B. Flesh firmness (N); C. Ripening Index*

266 Due to the limited number of samples ($N=120$), a methodology to define the boundaries is
 267 proposed. The boundaries limits may therefore vary when introducing new samples. The
 268 methodology used to assess them is nevertheless defined as follows: to minimise as much as
 269 possible any overlap between the three categories, and considering the results obtained in
 270 the classification model based on the FF criterion, it was decided that Class 2 should be the
 271 first one defined. For this purpose, the first quartile of Class 1 and the third quartile of Class
 272 3 were selected as the upper and lower limits of Class 2, respectively. This guarantees that
 273 no overripe avocados remain in this category and avoids food waste. The rest of the
 274 categories were defined as follows:

- 275 • $RI_{\text{Class 1}} < 0.55$
- 276 • $-0.28 \leq RI_{\text{Class 2}} < 0.55$
- 277 • $-0.28 \leq RI_{\text{Class 3}}$

278 Table 2 shows the confusion matrix between the actual classes and the re-classified groups,
 279 based in the RI. The actual classes are the ones defined by the warehouse based on

280 destructive sampling of FF in a small number of avocados. Results in the confusion matrix
 281 show the highest agreement for Class 1, with 97.50 % coincidence between the actual and
 282 the re-classified classes. In this case, only a 2.50 % of the samples classified by the warehouse
 283 as Class 1 were categorized as Class 2, and none as Class 3, based on the defined RI
 284 boundaries. However, Class 2 and Class 3 showed lower coincidence than Class 1. In Class 2,
 285 a lower consensus was found (50.00 %), with the 25.00 % of the samples classified as Class 1
 286 and the other 25.00 % as Class 3, according to the RI. The same happens in Class 3, which has
 287 62.50 % of coincidence. 32.50 % of the samples were reclassified as Class 2 and the 5.00 % as
 288 Class 1 by the RI.

289 *Table 2. Confusion matrix of avocado reclassification according to the ripening index (RI)*

		Reclassification			
		Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	TOTAL
Actual Classes	Class 1	97.50 %	2.50 %	0.00 %	100 %
	Class 2	25.00 %	50.00 %	25.00 %	100 %
	Class 3	5.00 %	32.50 %	62.50 %	100 %

290

291 *3.2. Results of the PLS-DA classification models to predict warehouse classes 1 to 3 (based on FF)*

292 After testing various pre-processing techniques, the best PLS-DA models were obtained with the
 293 Savitzky-Golay algorithm, using a second derivative and a polynomial of degree 3. Changes in
 294 the Wilk's lambda test statistic as a function of the window width in the Savitzky-Golzy algorithm
 295 showed that the best results were obtained with a window width of 47.

296 The PLS-DA classification model developed on the pre-processed spectra showed an accuracy of
 297 62 % with 6 LV. However, the confusion matrix (Table 3) and the model's metrics (Table 4) show
 298 differences in the classification performance of the different classes in the validation dataset.
 299 Extreme classes (Class 1 and 3), show better results, with a 100 % and a 65 % of well classified
 300 individuals, than the intermediate class (Class 2), which shows only a 20 % of well classified. It is
 301 especially noteworthy that most of the individuals (70 %) initially assigned to Class 2 are assigned

302 to Class 1 by the model and the 10 % to Class 3. These results are also reflected in the model's
 303 metrics, shown in Table 4. It indicates higher sensitivity for Class 1 (1.00) and Class 3 (0.65). The
 304 same happens with the F1-Score, with values of 0.67 and 0.74 for classes 1 and 3 respectively
 305 and 0.32 for Class 2.

306 *Table 3. Confusion matrix of the PLS-DA model using 6-7 LV in the validation dataset.*

		Predicted		
		Class 1	Class 2	Class 3
Actual	Class 1	100 %	0 %	0 %
	Class 2	70 %	20 %	10 %
	Class 3	30 %	5 %	65 %

307

308 *Table 4. Matrix of the PLS-DA model using 7 LV in the validation dataset.*

	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1-Score
Class 1	0.50	1.00	0.68	0.67
Class 2	0.80	0.20	0.97	0.32
Class 3	0.87	0.65	0.96	0.74

309

310 In Figure 3 the PLS-DA model output shows that the first score (X-axis direction) is well aligned
 311 to separate ripening classes, the higher the score the riper the fruit. In this Figure it can be seen
 312 that Class 1 and Class 3 are well separated, while Class 2 is mixed along the other two classes.
 313 This might be due to two reasons: i) fruit ripening is a continuous process, and thus, it should be
 314 treated as a continuous model instead of use a discrete model; ii) the definition of the Classes
 315 made only by testing the FF of a few samples is not enough to have a good separation of the
 316 three classes.

317

318 *Figure 3. Scores of the validation set ($N_{val} = 60$) predicted by a PLS-LDA using 6 LV. The large big stars and ellipses*
 319 *show the classes' centre of mass and the standard deviation of the calibration set ($N_{cal} = 60$).*

320

321 3.3. Results of PLSR for RI prediction.

322 Based on results from the previous PLS-DA classification model, it was decided that ripening
 323 could also be considered as a continuous process. Furthermore, since the classes redefined using
 324 the RI presented previously may vary when increasing the number of samples and depending
 325 on the warehouse operator, it was decided to build a regression model instead of another
 326 classification model. The warehouse could thus set its own boundaries ad hoc.

327 The best results for the PLSR models were achieved using SNV as a pre-processing procedure.
 328 Table 5 displays the summary statistics for the calibration and prediction PLSR models. The
 329 models were developed in the whole range of the spectrum, 380-2000 nm (Model 1), and in the
 330 spectral range of 400-1100 nm (Model 2).

331 Both models showed good performances (Table 5) in the CV, with R^2 values of 0.76 in both cases
 332 and a SECV of 0.47 and 0.48 respectively. The models showed acceptable bias in the CV, of -
 333 0.010 and 0.022.

334
335
336

Table 5. Results on PLSR in CV ($N_{CV} = 60$) and validation ($N_{val} = 60$) for Model 1 (380-2000 nm) and Model 2 (400-1100 nm). LV – number of Latent Variables; R^2 – Coefficient of determination for CV and validation; SE – standard error of CV and of prediction; RPD - residual predictive deviation for validation

		Wavelength range (nm)	LV	R^2	SE	Bias	RPD
Model 1	CV	380 - 2000	4	0.76	0.47	-0.0104	-
	Validation			0.62	0.69	1.22	1.60
Model 2	CV	400-1100	4	0.76	0.48	0.0224	-
	Validation			0.63	0.68	1.03	1.62

337

338 Though the models provided good results, they gave some errors:

- 339 - The bias and the slope in the validation showed high values of 1.22 and 0.52 respectively
340 for Model 1 and of 1.03 and 0.52 for Model 2 (Figure 4A and Figure 4C). This behaviour
341 is normal in quantitative NIR spectroscopy due to some block effects occurring between
342 the two measuring conditions. They can be corrected using several techniques, such as
343 bias and slope correction, piecewise direct standardization, or dynamic orthogonal
344 projection, to cite some. As an example, a bias and slope correction carried out on the
345 test set gives the following results: $R^2 = 0.62$; SEP = 0.86; bias = -0.0078 and RPD = 1.28,
346 for Model 1 and $R^2 = 0.63$; SEP = 0.84; bias = 0.00086 and RPD = 1.31, for Model 2 (Figure
347 4B and Figure 4D).

348

349 *Figure 4. Results on PLSR in validation ($N_{val} = 60$) on spectra pre-processed with Standard Normal Variate, before and*
 350 *after bias and slope correction. A. Model 1 (380-2000 nm) before bias and slope correction. B. Model 1 after bias and*
 351 *slope correction. C. Model 2 (400-1100 nm) before bias and slope correction. D. Model 2 after bias and slope*
 352 *correction.*

353

354 - A standard deviation of the error of 0.69 and 0.68 for Model 1 and Model 2 respectively
 355 (or 0.86 and 0.84 in the BS corrected results), which could be diminished by increasing
 356 the calibration database with new samples.

357

358 4. DISCUSSION

359 4.1. Discussion about the new ripening index

360 Avocado ripening is a complex process that presents inhomogeneity due to the large number of
361 pre- and postharvest factors that affect the fruit's metabolism (Bower and Cutting, 1988;
362 Hernández et al., 2016). A ripening prediction index that uses minimum inputs would hence be
363 beneficial for warehouses and processors with a view to improving postharvest management.
364 The ripening index presented in this work was inspired by previous works carried out such as
365 mango (see M & M section). In this case, the minimum number of quality parameters considered
366 necessary to determine avocado ripeness was two: DMC and FF.

367 DMC was selected even though our results revealed low correlation with the ripening classes,
368 as also found by Pedreschi et al. (2014). This has been related to the inactivation of acetyl-CoA
369 carboxylase once avocado has been harvested. This enzyme is for the production of long chain
370 fatty acids from [¹⁴C] acetate in avocado tissues (Villa-Rodriguez et al., 2011). DMC was
371 nevertheless not discarded, since it is correlated to oil content, which determines smoothness
372 and acceptance by consumers (Hofman et al., 2013).

373 On the other hand, FF shows a satisfactory correlation with ripeness evolution. Avocado
374 softening during ripening has been related with the activity of several enzymes such as
375 polygalacturonase (PG), pectin methylesterase (PME) and, cellulase (Villa-Rodriguez, et al.,
376 2011). The activity of these enzymes has been correlated with the respiratory climacteric and
377 ethylene (Pesis et al., 1978), that in avocado increases during postharvest until they reach the
378 maximum climacteric peak (Villa-Rodriguez, et al., 2011).

379 The proposed index is devoted to being used to define classes according to a more complete
380 information, based in more parameters than only FF. In this work the boundaries of three
381 ripening classes were selected. This was based on the available data and on the studied case of
382 a particular warehouse. The proof of concept of the methodology of choosing the boundaries
383 based on the new index is nevertheless established and can be replicated in future works at
384 different locations and under different conditions. The boundaries chosen should thus only be
385 considered for this particular case; for this index's application to the industry further research

386 would be needed, with a larger number of samples. Thus, the boundaries of the classes could
387 change. However, these boundaries could be used to redefine the three Classes (Class 1 –
388 unripe; Class 2 – medium ripeness; Class 3 – almost ripe).

389 This index was proved to be sensitive to NIR spectroscopy. However, it presented values of RPD
390 < 2 (RPD = 1.60, when using the whole wavelength range and RPD = 1.20, when using only the
391 wavelength range between 400-1100 nm). According to Saeys et al., 2005, these values indicate
392 that the predictions are adequate to assign classes instead of using them as a quantitative
393 prediction. Nevertheless, in some particular cases of industrial applications, such as the present
394 case, the accuracy of the quantitative predicted value is not so important as long as the range
395 that class belongs to is known.

396 *4.2. Wavelength influences on the PLS-DA and PLSR models*

397 To study and better understand the models, the spectral variables (wavelengths) making a
398 sizable contribution were analysed. This was done by means of the discriminant vector (VP1) in
399 the classification model and a representative curve of the regression coefficients in the PLSR
400 model.

401 In both models the visible part of the spectra makes the largest contribution. In the case of the
402 classification model, the VP1 alternates centred at 565 nm (Figure 5A). The coefficients of the
403 PLSR model have a peak at 540 nm (Figure 6). Eichhorn Bilodeau et al., 2019 associated the
404 wavelength range around 550 nm to anthocyanins. During the ripening process, anthocyanins
405 in the avocado' skin increase (Ashton et al., 2006), causing shifts at this wavelength. Moreover,
406 both models show peaks in the range of 620-760 nm, which has been associated to chlorophyll
407 absorption (Wellburn, 1994). Specifically, the PLSR model reveals a peak at 675 nm (Figure 6). In
408 the VP1 from the classification model, a positive peak at 665 nm is detected (Figure 5A). This
409 can be associated to chlorophyll a, which absorbs at 662 nm (Eichhorn Bilodeau et al., 2019).
410 Chlorophyll a and b increase during the ripening process in the dark green flesh just below the
411 skin, but not in the skin itself nor in the flesh (Ashton et al., 2006). Additionally, a negative peak

412 and a positive peak are found in the PLSDA and PLSR models respectively at 715 nm (Figures 5A
413 and 6). In PLSDA model, a sinusoidal profile can be seen centred at 715 nm, which is sensitive to
414 the horizontal position. As plant tissue, avocado skin spectra present a red edge related to
415 chlorophyll content, which decreases during ripening (Ashton et al., 2006).

416 The models differ in the NIR part of the spectra. The VP1 for the classification model shows that
417 the region between 900-1500 nm have a strong contribution to the model. A sinusoidal pattern
418 is found, with positive peaks at 1060 nm, 1285 nm and 1500 nm, and negative peaks at 970 nm,
419 1165 nm and 1390 nm (Figure 4B). These peaks are similar to those observed by Olerawaju et
420 al. (2016) in 'Hass' avocado. Peaks at 970 nm and 1165 nm could be associated to the H-O-H
421 stretching modes of water, while peaks around 1300 nm have been associated to the
422 determination of oil (Siesler et al., 2008). The different signs of these peaks suggest that they
423 are balanced and that the model may be using evolution of the water/oil relationship during
424 ripening. In the case of the regression coefficients curve (Figure 5), these peaks are less obvious,
425 though they also have different signs.

426 VP1 also presents a negative peak at 1390 nm, corresponding to a sinusoidal profile on the mean
427 spectrum. This peak may be related to water absorption, since water presents several
428 absorption peaks in the range of 1375-1385 nm (combination OH anti-symmetric stretch + OH
429 symmetric stretch) and 1450-1460 nm (first overtone) (Siesler et al., 2008), which can be shifted
430 due to changes in water state (Renati et al., 2019). The combination of the discriminant vector
431 peak and the sinusoidal profile of the spectra is sensitive to horizontal shifts. This suggests that
432 the classification model seems to be sensitive to subtle changes in water state.

433 On the coefficient curve from the PLSR model (Figure 6), the region between 1300-2000 nm
434 appears noisier than the VIS-NIR part (380-1100 nm). This might explain why Model 2 (400-1100
435 nm) slightly differs in its results from Model 1. This opens the door to move to a hand-held *cost-*
436 *effective* spectrometer in the range from 400-1100 nm to be used in the warehouse operative.

437 Nevertheless, the regions between 1370-1450 nm present some contribution to the model. This
438 region has been associated by previous authors to oil determination. On the coefficient curve
439 from the PLSR model (Figure 6), the regions between 1370-1515 nm and 1560-1765 nm present
440 a contribution to the model. Both regions have been associated by previous authors to oil
441 determination (Wedding et al., 2013; Olarewaju et al., 2016). This agrees with the fact that the
442 regression model is based on the RI that includes the contribution of DMC, which is correlated
443 with oil (Hofman, 2013).
444

A

B

445 *Figure 5. Discriminant vector 1 (VP1) of the PLS-DA and the mean differentiated spectrum (N=60) after Savitzky-*
 446 *Golay algorithm, using a second derivative and a polynomial of degree 3, with a window width of 47 spectral pre-*
 447 *processing. A. in the VIS-NIR region (380-850 nm) B. in the near infrared part (1100-1500 nm)*

448

449

450 *Figure 6. Regression coefficients of the PLS model performed on the whole wavelength range (380-2000 nm), with 4*
451 *LV, after Standard Normal Variate (SNV) spectral pre-processing using Standard Normal Variate*

452

453 **CONCLUSIONS**

454 This paper shows a non-destructive method to classify avocados in three classes predefined by
455 a warehouse, based on FF tests, performed on a small number of avocados, by means of NIR
456 spectroscopy and a PLS-DA classifier. The results are promising in terms of NIR spectroscopy is
457 able to distinguish extreme classes. Nevertheless, it was considered that not only FF was
458 involved in ripening, but also other factors such as DMC. Thus, a new ripening index was
459 proposed, based in FF and DMC to redefine the ripening classes. The aim was thus to show a
460 proof of concept of the potentiality for use of this index. Therefore, a PLS regression model was
461 proposed using the RI. The reasons for building a regression model and not another classification
462 model were the following: i) ripening was considered as a continuous process; ii) the classes and
463 class boundaries defined in this work may vary when increasing the number of samples and
464 depending on the warehouse operator. The regression models were developed using the whole
465 wavelength range, but also using a small part of the spectrum (400-1100 nm) with the aim to
466 study the potentiality of moving to a more *cost-effective* system easy to implement in the
467 warehouse operative in the future.

468 Even though the limited number of samples used for this work, all the models were validated in
469 an independent dataset, with fruit coming from a different origin from those used in the
470 calibration dataset. Thus, this work shows the ability of Vis-NIR spectroscopy to classify avocados
471 at different postharvest ripeness stages.

472

473

474 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

475 Conceptualization: A.M.H, J.M.R, I.O.; Data curation: A.M.H., J.M.R; Formal analysis: A.M.H.,
476 J.M.R; Funding acquisition: I.O., J.Z; Investigation: A.M.H., S.N., I.O., M.G., A.V., N.G., J.M.R;
477 Methodology: A.M.H., I.O., M.G., A.V., J.M.R; Project administration: I.O; Software: N.G., J.M.R;
478 Supervision: J.M.R.; Validation: A.M.H., J.M.R.; Visualization: A.M.H, J.M.R; Roles/Writing:
479 A.M.H, J.M.R; Writing, review & editing: A.M.H, S.N., I.O., M.G., A.V., J.Z., N.G., J.M.R.

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